

Bitcoin, the Blockchain and Beyond

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Author biography

Jean-Luc Verhelst Jean-Luc Verhelst is the author of *Bitcoin, the Blockchain and Beyond* and works as a strategy and blockchain consultant for Monitor Deloitte. He delivered multi-day trainings in EMEA and USA. He won the world's largest blockchain hackathon of 2016 and his master thesis on Bitcoin received the award for best financial thesis of 2014 in Belgium. He founded the think-tank BlockchainHub Brussels and holds degrees in IT and Business. Most importantly, Jean-Luc has a real passion for Bitcoin, blockchains and how they will shape our future. He is also a well-regarded public speaker on Bitcoin and the Blockchain, having addressed audience up to 3000 people. Through the course of the years, Jean-Luc has helped multiple companies, executives, crypto-currency enthusiasts, and politicians with the understanding of this amazing technology and what it could mean for them. With his book, he hopes to bring his knowledge to the masses, in a simple yet effective way.

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